

Political Liberalism in a Polarized Religious and Democratic Setting: The Case of Nigeria

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Abstract

The validity of any theory whether scientific or religious is better understood and appreciated when it is applied in specific socio-cultural, political, economic or religious contexts. Thus, the paper examined the theory of political liberalism against the backdrop of a heavily polarized religious and democratic setting as Nigeria. This was necessary because as a nation, Nigeria consists of three constitutionally recognized religions namely: Islam, Christianity and African Traditional Religion with Muslims and Christians forming majority and always competing for hegemony. This peculiar nature of religious configuration and the quest for hegemony amongst members of Christianity and Islam often generate suspicion, bigotry, agitations, and religious and political tensions. Regrettably, over the years, the inability of political leaders to adequately manage Nigeria's religious diversity has put religion at the front burner in all socio-economic and political issues. Using the discursive approach in analyzing key liberal theories, the paper revealed four liberal paradigms that are useful in addressing the Nigerian situation namely primary goods, religious neutrality, equal recognition of religions, and reasonable citizenship. The paper recommends the application of these liberal paradigms in managing Nigeria's polarized religious configuration.

Keywords: Political Liberalism, Polarized, Religious, Democratic, Setting and Nigeria

Introduction

One major problem confronting contemporary academics is not the lack of theorizing or formulation of theories instead it is the lack of application of such academic theories to real life situations. One area in which this has manifested prominently is in the area of applying religious theories to real religious situations. There are several academic theories of religion today especially with regards to the Nigerian situation. However, not many of these theories have been adequately applied or are applicable to the highly polarized religious setting in Nigeria. As a religiously pluralistic country, Nigeria consists of three prominent religions namely African Traditional Religion, Islam and Christianity. Population records cited in Koko showed that Muslims and Christians have almost equal population and exist on a north-south dichotomy. For example, a 2001 report on International Religious Freedom on Nigeria from *The World Facts Book by CIA* puts the number of Muslims at 50%, Christians at 40% and Indigenous religionists at 10%. On a related development, the 2010's census of Association of Religion Data Archives indicates a slight change of the above projection. The report shows that the population of Christians is approximately 46.5%, while that of Muslims is 45.5% and followers of other religions are put at 7.7%. Similarly, a report of December 18, 2012 carried out by the Pew and Research Center on "religion and public life" indicates that in 2010, the population of Muslims and Christians slightly rose to 48.8% and 49.3% respectively, while that of indigenous and other religions declined to 1.9%.¹

Suffice it to state that though the above figures are contestable for lack of clearly tested data; it does clearly make Nigeria the "greatest Islamo-Christian Nation" in the world or better still, a pivotal state as scholars have

observed.² Unarguably, such a large number of Muslims and Christians having almost equal population and living side by side obviously make Nigeria a country with one of the most complicated religious configuration as far as religious pluralism is concerned. Ordinarily, this form of religious pluralism should serve as an added advantage and not constitute a problem for Nigeria following the rich moral and ethical teachings of these religions. Regrettably, due to mismanagement it has become a major crises ridden factor that impacts negatively on decision and policy making processes especially in the current democratic dispensation. Therefore, the paper examined the relevance of John Rawls' paradigm of political liberalism in addressing the heavily polarized religious situation in the current democratic dispensation in Nigeria. To achieve its purpose, the paper adopted the discursive approach in analyzing data gathered through personal observation and extensive review of liberal theories. The kernel of this paper is that religion as it were, is one of Nigeria's hydra-headed monsters that require to be tackled headlong if socio-economic and political development would be achieved. And one most viable way to address it is by the application of John Rawls' political liberal principles of pluralism in the Nigerian context. For purpose of clarity, the next section will be devoted to analyzing the polarized religious setting in Nigerian's current democratic situation.

Conceptualizing the Polarized Religious Situation in Nigeria's Current Democracy

The fact that Nigeria has been and continues to be polarized along religious lines is not strange even to the casual observer. However, this polarization phenomenon of Nigeria along religious lines appears to have taken different forms in the current democratic dispensation particularly since the country returned to democratic rule in 1999. To be clear, the terms "polarized" and "democracy" needs to be placed in their proper context. To start with, the term "polarized" is defined by the New International Webster's Comprehensive Dictionary of the English Language as something pertaining to a group or situation being at two or more extremes.³ One unavoidable implication of this definition is that the word polarized has something to do with a group being divided into two or more extremes. Accordingly, it is used here to refer to the tendency to cause a group to be divided into extremes, or a phenomenon in which a group is caused to be divided into two or more extremes. In this context, it specifically refers to a situation in which Nigerians are divided along the lines of religion: Islam and Christianity.

On the contrast, the term "democracy" has been variously conceived and defined in different ways. This is probably due to the widespread notion that democracy is the best form of government. Consequently, the same dictionary defined it as a theory of government which, in its purest form, holds that the state should be controlled by all the people, each sharing equally in privileges, duties, and responsibilities and each participating in person in the government, as in the city-states of ancient Greece.⁴ The interesting thing about the above definition is that it identifies three indispensable features of a truly democratic government to include: one, control of the state by all the people. This means that a truly democratic state is the one in which all the people irrespective of gender, class, religion and ethnicity have equal control over the affairs of such a state; two, each person shares equal privileges, duties, and responsibilities. In other words, in a genuine democratic state, all citizens have equal access to basic needs of life. Citizens in such a democratic context are not discriminated on the basis of social class, ethnic or religious affiliations; instead they have equal access and rights to socio-economic opportunities such as employment, shelter, political appointments, education, medical services, etc.; and third, each person fully participates in the affairs of governance. This means that in a truly democratic government, citizens are usually consulted before decisions are taken by those in authority. The relationship between leaders and followers is such

a democratic context is not that of master-servant, but that of equals. This in part explains why Becker and Raveloson conceived democracy as “government of the people or government of the majority.”⁵

It is not misleading therefore to state that one significant difference that emerges from the above definition between democracies on the one hand and monarchy, aristocracy and dictatorship on the other hand is that the former is legitimized by voting through electioneering processes, while the later are achieved by inheritance, imposition or selection. Again, in democracy, the people are the primary and central reason for governance whereas in aristocracy, monarchy and dictatorship, power and authority resides on the political leader who in most cases sees himself as a demi-god. It is in line with these differences that Abraham Lincoln had provided one of the most widely accepted definitions of democracy as “the government of the people, by the people and for the people.”⁶ Following this, some proponents of democracy have hinged their untiring support for it on the ground of certain fundamental principles which include promotion of human rights and freedom, seasonal elections, rule of law, separation of powers, fairness, equity, justice, etc.⁷ Similarly, Dunn has highlighted some indispensable principles of democracy to include freedom and equality of all citizens, supremacy of the rule of law and a commitment to the progress of the political entity.⁸ In essence, a state can only be said to be democratic if such a state or society recognizes the differences in human interests and strives to provide the basic structures required to meeting such needs using politics as the sphere of negotiation.⁹

Unfortunately, in the Nigerian democratic situation, some if not all of these basic tenets of a true democratic state are obviously lacking. What has emerged in Nigeria instead is a form of pseudo-democracy or at best civilian rule that allows high level corruption, impunity, poverty, unemployment, insecurity, political thuggery and religious bigotry to thrive, thereby leaving citizens with no alternative than to resort to religion as a source of succor. This point is stressed by Oteh and Eze who argued that citizens resort to other forms of identities because the state is unable to provide their basic needs and where this occurs, perennial social tension, political instability and destruction of life and property becomes inevitable¹⁰ as it is today. Ordinarily with the advent of democracy from 1999 till date, the above indispensable and widely accepted principles of a true democratic society ought to have been entrenched in Nigeria’s socio-economic and political affairs. Regrettably, this is not the case as the country has continued to be bedeviled by intractable challenges occasioned amongst other things by the inability of those in political leadership to properly manage the country’s religious differences. Thus, in a sense it is the inability of political leaders to appropriately manage Nigeria’s complex religious diversity that has further polarized the country along religious lines in the present democratic dispensation as Koko correctly observed.¹¹ One area in which the mismanagement of religion has manifested prominently in Nigeria is in politicization of religion. In fact, beginning from 1999 till date, the phenomenon of politicization of religion has been one main reason why citizens are polarized along religious lines in the country as some scholars have also rightly noted.¹²

It is safe to argue then that Nigeria is deeply polarized along religious lines in this current democratic dispensation because there is marked absence of the principles of liberal democracy in the country. What this apparently means is that there is a strong connection between religious diversity and democracy. And this relationship is such that where the former is properly managed, the later becomes fruitful. Perhaps, to be more precise is to argue that where the former is mismanaged in any given democratic context, the dividends of the later becomes difficult to achieve no matter how promising they may be as the situation in Nigeria has clearly demonstrated. In this way, what makes democracy to thrive in any given context is not simply because it is a

system of government that has the capacity to guarantee and protect citizens' aspirations and welfare, but because its key drivers.

In this case the political class upholds the rule of law and eschew all forms of religious sentiments, bigotry, and practices that are inimical to true democratic tenets. Indeed, this is one major area that differentiates developed democracies of the western world from the pseudo-democracies in Africa and particularly Nigeria. In western democracies, political leaders bracket their religious predispositions while carrying out their political responsibilities, whereas in Nigeria political leaders usually jettison the principles of managing religious diversity namely respect for all religions, freedom of religions, neutrality, equal recognition, etc. for their personal religious gains. This possibly explains why the twenty-four years democracy in Nigeria has been characterized by endemic corruption, adverse poverty, massive unemployment, threatening insecurity, infrastructural decay and to say the least divisive tendencies. Therefore, Nigeria needs the application of certain indispensable liberal democratic principles to address the problem of polarization of citizens along religious lines. In the next section, we shall examine two dominant liberal democratic paradigms that have been advocated by scholars in dealing with religious diversity.

Liberalists' Perspectives on Polarized Religious and Democratic Settings

Various perspectives have been expressed by liberalists who sought to understand the challenges faced by polarized religious and democratic settings. For purpose of clarity, it is safe to classify the various views into two dominant ones. The first in this classification is what we may best refer to as *religion-state dichotomy paradigm*. It is so called because liberal scholars in this classification advocates for a strict separation between religion and state and in extreme cases insist that religion should be expunged from the public space of liberal democratic states if peace, stability and development must be achieved. Most outstanding promoter of this liberal paradigm is John Rawls whom we shall devote the last section of this paper to extensively discuss his liberal paradigms.

However, others who have contributed to the debate on religion and state dichotomy paradigm include Novak, Iannaccone and Berman, Corduan, etc. For example, Novak in his work, *The Spirit of Democratic Capitalism*, defended a thin conception of the good by distinguishing "democratic capitalism" from traditionalist and socialist schemes which he believed attempted to produce a close society whose unitary order is held together by a collective vision of the good. He argued that a unitary moral order will inadvertently give rise to a unitary political power that will seek to impose its concept of the good on all citizens and this for him is inconsistent with maintaining a stable democratic society. Hence, he opted for a free, pluralistic society in which public virtues depend only upon the cooperation of free individuals. Consequently, he introduced the concept of the *empty shrine paradigm* which he believed displays a "reverential emptiness at the heart of pluralism."¹³ This emptiness by his estimation is the respect for "transcendence" and not the usual skeptical attitude of liberal thinkers regarding matters of ultimate concern. He argued very strongly that there is no one sacred canopy in a genuinely pluralistic society. Moreover, Novak concluded that there is usually no one world, image or symbol representing a particular religious ideology for which all are to seek, instead, the public space is usually empty. Its emptiness represents the transcendence, which all free consciences are to approach from virtually infinite number of directions.¹⁴ Suffice it to state that one serious implication of the empty shrine paradigm as it were is that the public space of liberal democratic states should be left empty without the domination of either one or some religious ideologies. Therefore, with this sort of argument, the notion of completely expunging religion from the public space was accordingly advocated as possible solution.

Drawing heavily from the empty shrine model, Iannaccone and Berman in “Religious Extremism: The Good, the Bad and the Deadly”, argued that divergent religious confessions have the tendency to hinder a true national identity and as such cannot promote mutual co-existence in liberal democratic societies. Hence, they advocated for a strict separation of the religion and the state in such a way that religious confessions are not allowed into the public space.¹⁵ This point has also been made by Corduan, who insisted that liberal states should eschew at all cost policies that attempt to accommodate exclusive truth claims because they are inconsistent with liberal principles, particularly, the principle of inclusivity.¹⁶ What this implies is that one of the major reasons why religiously pluralistic states are heavily polarized is because some religious people usually hold exclusive claims about the religions they professed without understanding the principles guarding liberal societies. In this vein therefore, the only alternative available is to ensure that competing religious claims are eradicated or not allowed to find their way to the public space.

One crucial way to achieve this as Gordon, a liberal pluralist explained is to allow equal treatment and individual meritocracy to override individual’s religious affiliation.¹⁷ However, it should be stated that one major problem with the religion and state dichotomy paradigm is that it attempts to paint a very ugly picture of religion as evil without also noting the important role which religion plays in human society. Apparently, Nash tilted towards this direction when he observed that the best way to deal with people holding divergent religious views is not by advocating for a public space devoid of religion but by being tolerant to all views.¹⁸ Suffice it to state that while tolerance is a virtue worth embracing, the extent to which the state should tolerate extreme religious positions that are capable of destabilizing it remains a matter of serious concern.

The second dominant liberal view which attempts to address the challenges of divergent religious ideologies in polarized religious situations is what may be fittingly referred to as *religion-state no dichotomy paradigm*. It is so called because as a theory, it insists that the challenges of religious diversity cannot be simply resolved by attempting to expunge religion or religious confessions from the public space of liberal states, hence, it opts for a type of liberal state in which religious diversity is allowed to thrive at the public space. There are innumerable liberal scholars who hold strongly to this view but for purpose of space, only a few would be considered.

The first on the list is Tocqueville, a nineteenth century French philosopher who in his work *Democracy in America*, argued that social and democratic order is impossible in a religiously pluralistic society without reference to religious faith because the principle of individual freedom and liberty anchors on religion, particularly Christianity. He arrived at this position because he believed that one outstanding virtue of Christianity is that it sees all citizens as equal before the law as well as promotes virtues of compassion, humanity and forgiveness. Consequently, he enjoined defenders of individual freedom to invoke the aid of religion at the public space because without it freedom would be impossible, social and democratic order would become a mirage and public morality would be eroded.¹⁹ The crux of Tocqueville’s position is that religion plays significant role not just in individuals’ lives but also in the affairs of liberal democratic states. Hence, he strongly pushed for a liberal democratic state in which religion and state are not separated and religion to a large extent influences public policy and democratic norms. However, the problem with his view as Cliteur observed is that it tends to contradict the very principle of equality of conditions which he purported to promote by exalting Christianity above other religious confessions.²⁰

Adding to the theory of religion and state no-dichotomy paradigm, Habermas in his works “Religion in the Public Sphere” (2006), “Faith and Knowledge” (2003) and “Intolerance and Discrimination” (2003) defended

a view in which the interplay of religion and the state is seen as inseparably dovetailing on the ground that religion plays significant role at the public space judging from the experience of the fall of the Soviet Union and the September 11, 2001 attack on the US. He noted for example that the variants of religious fundamentalism in the Middle East, Africa, Southeast Asia and Indian that often results to national and ethical conflicts and terrorism attests to the fact that religion wields strong political influence in modern societies and as such requires a renewed consideration. Consequently, he dispelled the theory of secularism and opted for what he referred to as “deliberative mode of democratic will formation” which he believed guarantees equal freedom for all religions.²¹ With this deliberative hypothesis, Habermas therefore completely rejected any likely suggestion of secular model as alternative to the challenges of religious diversity in polarized religious and democratic settings on the ground that secularism tends to promote a society in which religion is relegated to the background and public morality becomes unattainable. However, the difficulty with his view is that it tilts towards presenting a thin view of religion and places a huge burden on both religious and secular persons as Braeckman, Sheedy and Cooke observed.²²

On a related development, Mouw and Griffioen have observed that religiously pluralistic states are usually characterized by relativistic and directional pluralists- both referring to people holding divergent religious ideologies who may find it very difficult to co-exist in a common political framework with people of other competing viewpoints. They argued that since public life relates to issues of common good, then religiously pluralistic states would probably face the challenge of disunity and instability resulting from these competing ideologies. Therefore, they concluded that real unity in such a religiously polarized context may require more than the strict separation of religion and state to include dependence on the transcendent since the beauty of nature lies partly in its diversity.²³ What these liberal scholars tended to establish in essence is that the challenges confronting religiously diverse states cannot be resolved merely by strict secularist theories because humans are naturally created with tendencies to hold divergent views. Hence, there should be no dichotomy between religion and the state, instead the kind of pluralism that allows for equality and freedom of religions should be encouraged. This is however, misleading because the challenges of religious ideologies may not be easily addressed simply by allowing religious confessions at the public space. In fact, experience have shown that religious ideologies are the most difficult to address since it involves issues of faith and personal conviction that may not sit well with the views of others.

In corroborating with other scholars, Romus believed that the essential condition for national integration in any nation-state rests on the general will of the people and not on the homogeneous configuration of the people as some liberal scholars assumed. He argued that efforts towards creating a mono-identity based on religion or otherwise in a polarized religious setting would amount to an ideological manipulation and oppression of the plural identities of the people and this could provoke the worst type of bigotry, fanaticism, violence and oppression. He noted that the essence of pluralism is for religious communities to use the richness of their religious convictions, inspirations, spiritual and moral values for the welfare of all. Thus, he opted for a kind of meaningful religious dialogue that promotes the true value of religious pluralism. Such pluralism is the one that accepts the legitimacy of all religious traditions and sees their followers as equal partners in religious and secular affairs of common human concern in the political society. Moreover, he concluded that sustainable harmony and national solidarity among citizens in polarized religious contexts can only be attained by entrenching permanent ethical values which protect human persons in their dignity as moral subjects and social beings.²⁴ In essence, Romus is also of the view that the challenges of religious diversity may not simply be addressed by proposing a strict dichotomy between religion and state, hence he advocated for all inclusive religious dialogue.

On his part, Kalami in his eloquent article “Religion in a Pluralistic Society” observed that secularism as a modern ideology is discriminatory and incapable of entrenching the kind of religiousness that religiously pluralistic society require. Accordingly, he appealed to pluralism as a viable alternative of the secularist model for two main reasons. First, it addresses practical issues and is consistent with the fact of human life. Second, because pluralism can provide influences, which strengthen the social bonds of the society.²⁵ Sahliyah in his article “Religious Resurgence and Political Modernization” has corroborated this position by rejecting the secularization and modernization theories which describe religion as something that would eventually fade away with time. He also debunked the assertion that the spread of scientific knowledge and modern communications would lead to the diminishing of religious beliefs. For him, modern realities in the world have shown that religion has continued to occupy the center stage of politics in many countries of the world. Therefore, he concluded that the recurrent religious crises which confront modern societies can be addressed by endorsing pluralism and not secularism.²⁶ The implication of this argument is that Kalami most certainly endorsed the inseparability of religion from the public space of liberal democratic states.

Furthermore, In “The Stubborn Persistence of Religion in the Global Arena,” Shupe showed how organized religion has stubbornly continued to influence national and international politics. He noted that secularization as a process assumes that society is gradually moving from some sacred condition to non-religious conditions but the opposite is the case. What has emerged instead are inter-religious hostilities which have created insatiable need for a search for ultimate meaning and values for which religion serves as a powerful tool for legitimacy, social cohesion and meaning. Following the influence of religion at the global arena, Shupe concluded that religion should be given the same attention as the economy, the polity and the community.²⁷ In an earlier work titled *The Naked Public Square: Religion and Democracy in America*, Neuhaus had offered a sustained critique of liberalists who attempted to expunge religious influences from public life noting that such efforts are inconsistent with liberal plural states because they apparently tend to create public persons that are anonymous, irrational and who only define justice behind a “veil of ignorance”. Hence, he opted for the adoption of pluralism instead of secularism.²⁸

A similar view is expressed by Newbigin in his work titled, *Foolishness to the Greeks*, where he resisted the hope for an empty shrine paradigm noting that the insistence for a strict dichotomy between the public and private realms is inimical to public morality.²⁹ It is important to state that this paper does not subscribe to liberal views which seeks to expunge religion completely from the public space. On the contrary it does not also endorse liberal views which indiscriminately give legitimacy to the saturation of religious ideologies at the public space of religious plural states. It argues that if religion should be allowed to play a role at the public space then certain indispensable principles of political liberalism must be strictly adhered to. These principles are enshrined in Rawls’ paradigm of political liberalism. In the last section, these liberal principles would be accordingly discussed.

Relevance of Rawls’ Liberal Paradigm in a Polarized Religious and Democratic Nigeria

As a theory, Rawls’s paradigm of political liberalism centers on how the issue of religion and its recognition at the public space or by the government should be addressed. Its primary focus is on how to properly manage religious pluralism amidst various competing religious ideologies of modern plural societies. Thus, as a starting point, this version of political liberalism generally recognizes pluralisms: moral, religious and philosophical as a natural phenomenon in modern societies. However, it insists that for stability, peace and development to take place in modern plural societies, certain indispensable principles must characterize such modern liberal democratic societies.³⁰ There are several models of these indispensable liberal democratic principles of Rawls that have emerged but here we shall examine a few of them for lack of space.

The first on the list of these liberal principles is the fact that Rawls' political liberalism insists that proper management of religious pluralism depends largely on the freedom and equality of all citizens. For purpose of clarity, it is safe to refer to this as *equal recognition paradigm*. It is so called because it insists that in liberal democratic societies with divergent identities, recognition of particularity of identities should be avoided at all costs while due recognition should be ascribed to individuals as citizens without recourse to their cultural, religious or social identities which constitute such a liberal society. What is required instead is for the state to guarantee the freedom and equality of all citizens at all times.³¹ The implication of this as Koko explained is that government officials in the exercise of their responsibilities and religious rights should adhere strictly to the principle of equal recognition not only of all citizens but also all religions as well as avoid discriminatory tendencies that can pose distrust amongst members of the diverse religious groups in Nigeria.³² As Taylor correctly argued that due recognition is not only a duty we owe people but a right that we must give to all human beings not minding their age, colour, language, culture and religion.³³ Unfortunately, in the Nigerian situation, discrimination of citizens based on religious affiliations has been and continues to be a common phenomenon. Even in extreme cases, particularly the northern part of the country the freedom of religions is unambiguously lacking and it accounts for why interreligious crises have become commonplace in northern Nigeria.

Closely related to the above is the fact that Rawls also argued that liberal democratic societies with competing religious identities should prioritize fair distribution of citizens' basic liberties over religious identities. These basic liberties are classified under what is described as the primary goods- that is, things that are requisite for social cooperation and the pursuit of the good life.³⁴ For purpose of clarity, it is necessary to refer to this second principle as *primary goods paradigm*. These in their order of priority include: first, the basic liberties for example: freedom of thought and liberty of conscience; freedom of association; and the freedom defined by the liberty and integrity of the person, as well as by the rule of law; and finally the political liberties; second, freedom of movement and free choice of occupation against a background of diverse opportunities; third, powers and prerogatives of offices and positions of responsibility, particularly those in the main political and economic institutions; fourth, income and wealth; and Fifth, the social basis of respect.

These principles of primary goods are believed to be fair and independent. Rawls observed that even though citizens differ in their views about the good life, they however, necessarily hold these five principles of primary goods in common.³⁵ And it is these that guarantee stability and social cooperation in pluralistic societies.³⁶ Regrettably in Nigeria, the inability of political leaders to provide the primary goods or basic amenities for citizens partly accounts for why citizens resort to religious for succour and where this occurs, religious crisis and divisive tendencies becomes inevitable. Thus, to address the polarized religious situation in Nigeria, there is need for political leaders or government to adhere to the primary goods paradigm by providing the basic liberties and social amenities for all citizens.

Furthermore, Rawls' theory of political liberalism also insisted that citizens in such a society of conflicting religious, moral and philosophical ideologies must treat their fellow citizens simply as citizens without recourse to religion. Although individuals are free to hold on to what they consider as valuable and important. They must however, conduct their daily affairs within the purview of public reason.³⁷ Such reason is considered public for three main reasons: one, because all free and equal citizens hold in common; two, because it is primarily concerned about political justice; third, because it meets the principle of mutuality, i.e. the belief that the reasons we would offer for our political actions are sufficient and reasonable not only to us but also to others.³⁸ It is fitting to refer to this principle as *public reason* and *equal citizenship paradigms*. It is so called because this principle tasks religious people to conduct their affairs within the purview of human reason and not on the basis of their religious affiliations and doctrines. Moreover, citizens in such liberal democratic states are to treat one another as equal citizens without recourse to what religious denominations they are affiliated. And it is this that guarantees peace, stability and mutual co-existence amongst religious citizens of liberal democratic states with competing religious identities.

Finally, Rawls also explained that public reason neither attacks nor imposes religious doctrines on others. Public reason applies to discourse of judges especially of a supreme court; discourse of government officials, especially chief executives and legislators; and discourse of public officers and their campaign managers, especially in their public oratory, party platforms, and political statements. Citizens are also required to heed to public reason when exercising their civic responsibility especially during voting. However, they are not bound by it if they are involved in other private activities such as religious worship, carrying out research, performing on stage and so on.³⁹ Again, it is safe to refer to this last principle as *religious neutrality paradigm* because it presupposes that a liberal state without religious persons is possible. Thus, it identifies two spheres of human activities that are possible in liberal societies. The first is the private sphere namely the family, church, mosques and synagogues where citizens are allowed to exercise their religious beliefs.

The second is the public space which includes educational institutions, judiciary, national assembly, political campaign ground, the police, army, and market places. Here citizens are not allowed to introduce their religious doctrines and beliefs especially while relating with other citizens of other religious affiliations. In fact, citizens should be treated simply as citizens without recourse to religion at the public space. Therefore, for Rawls, religious ideologies should not be introduced at the public space at all directly or indirectly instead citizens should simply treat themselves as citizens without recourse to religious affiliations when relating with each other. However, they are free to hold to their religious ideologies at the private sphere. With these principles, Rawls believed that the problem of polarization of citizens occasioned by competing religious ideologies could be successfully addressed in heavily religiously diverse liberal democratic societies. This theory has been successful in the U.S, UK, France, Netherlands, Indonesia, among others.

It is crucial to observe that Rawls' paradigm of political liberalism has been faced with fierce criticisms from different quarters for which this paper may not consider for purpose of space. Notwithstanding, these principles are apparently useful in Nigeria if applied because they explained ways to properly manage religious pluralism with a view to achieving political stability and social co-operation. In particular, Rawls' paradigms propose a plural state in which citizens are undifferentiated with respect to religious, moral, and philosophical ideologies. Thus, his political liberalism model can promote nationalism and patriotism amongst citizens as well as address the unfortunate abuses of religious pluralism in Nigeria's public space.

Conclusion

Religion has undoubtedly become a hydra-headed monster in Nigeria and accounts for some of the socio-economic and political problems bedeviling the country in the current democratic dispensation. This is due to inability of political leaders or government on the one hand and religious citizens on the other to play by the rules of modern liberal democracies. Consequently there are noticeable abuses of religion by citizens which include politicization of religion by political leaders and religionisation of politics by religious leaders, discrimination tendencies based on religious affiliations, unequal recognition of religions by government, human rights abuses as a result of religious practices, etc. These are inimical to maintaining the expected peace, stability and development which modern liberal democracies offer. Hence, the Nigerian state is currently polarized along religious lines especially between Christians and Muslims. To address this problem headlong therefore, Nigeria requires full implementation of Rawls' four paradigms of political liberalism namely: equal recognition, primary goods, public reason and equal citizenship, and religious neutrality which strongly advocated for a kind of liberal democratic society that allows citizens to be treated as citizens without recourse to religious affiliations. This is one of the most viable ways to address the problem of polarization of citizens orchestrated by the abuses of religious pluralism in Nigeria.

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